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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“TARATAKAN A ORAY”

Once upon a time, a powerful kingdom and never been invaded, Taratakan a Oray, was once attacked by nature’s wrath for the people predict as if it’s the end of the world for the giant waves were rolling the shore, mountains were loomed with darkness, a strong blows of wind were crossing around, lightning flashed as fast as one blink of an eye, and the land crumbled by an earthquake.

The kingdom is headed by a datu named Ayonan sa Darimbang with his better-half Bae a Labi Bolentay Pendilabi. The queen was in the throes of childbirth when the striking phenomenon hit the place.

The king summoned a meeting, requesting the presence of Batara Towan Pakir, a fortuneteller, to discuss matters about the enchantment that was bewitching their very own kingdom by consulting the ancient book of prophecy, the book of Omens.

Batara Towan Pakir exclaimed that these signs did not portend to the end of the world but to the importance of an event taking place: the birth of a son to their mighty king! This newborn prince marked to become the most powerful ruler, the fame and glory to their mighty kingdom.

Suddenly, the people of Taratakan a Oray turned with pride to the newly born prince until they had observed that the baby could hardly breathe as the condition was getting worse as something seemed to block the air from entering his body, endangering him.

Ayonan made a solemn vow promising that if the newborn child survives the difficult situation then he would abdicate the throne in his favor so as to enthrone him as the new Ayonan of Darimbang.

As time passed by, the child grew strong and very active around the lama of Torogan. The royal vow of the king had to be fulfilled as sworn.

Batara sa Damedag finally proclaimed Kanakan sa Marogong as the new Ayonan sa Darimbang of Taratakan a Oray. He gave advices to the newly crowned as follows: 1) Treat your people with kindness and preserve our customs and tradition; 2) Never require or decide something by force; 3) when you hear trouble brewing your people, settle the fight as fast as you can; 4) look for the individual situation of your people because you are obliged to share your wealth. His father added “I believe it is now the proper time for you explore around all the rich powerful kingdom in all regions of our place to find a high-ranking princess, a truly beautiful one who can match as in point of rank, in purity of ancestry as well as great wealth and power and offer a marriage proposal for we have enough wealth to fill any kingdom as dowry for your prospective bride.

Dariday sa Marogong went to Lakongan Malipantaw. He decided to rest under the shade of the tree. On top of the tree, the noris were in animated conversation. They were busy discussing the very beautiful princess named Taming Oray Masaleg, the Inambayanan a Oray of Iliyan a Bembaran. No one have seen this princess for she was hidden in the Lamin in Bangkonaw a Madanding in the highest heavens by Magaraay Anonen. The nori of Rapetan exclaimed that he heard this strange story from no one but her own nori herself, the Sampiri sa Bembaran – the nori of the fair princess.

Upon hearing this, he returned to his kingdom and informed his father about the beautiful princess he shall soon marry. His father was very delighted and called for an assembly of all the respected Datus to discuss best strategy to incorporate in the search for the Lamin of the one chosen to be courted by the young king.

Pengganapa Darimbang informed all the respected Datu in the resplendent Torogan that they were gathered on that auspicious day because of the dream of our Toto'o a Liyamin (sister of Dariday sa Marogong) as well as the secret grief of the young king.

"I dreamt of, as if it really happened on my crescent-shaped royal bed, a royal princess as bright as the sun who was in deep sleep had finally awakened and together, we enjoyed chewing the well-prepared betel quid. Nothing could detract me from my joy for I was convinced that this beautiful princess, a high ranking and unmatched among all our ladies, would add to our renown and raise the glory of our kingdom. Entertaining this thought brought grief to my heart and caused my tears to flow. Kindly plan now, my respected Datus where to locate the powerful kingdom of this beautiful princess within the space of a year for if you cannot find the place then it will surely cause me to get sick and death," lamented by the Princess Toto'o o Liyamin.

"I was in a semi-conscious state, began to dream a truly puzzling dream. It seemed that I had gone to a faraway foreign kingdom. By the vast shore of the sea, there I engaged in bloody battle with the handsome Datu as swift as a bird fighting on the battle field." I was awakened and went back to my big crescent-shaped luxurious bed and went back to sleep then my dream continued. This time, an army had come to invade our powerful kingdom as their purpose here in Taratakan a Oray is to capture the very beautiful princess that I myself was forcedly ordered to bring her out. O my respected Datus, I was obliged to protect this very beautiful lady for it would have been shameful if I would not do so," cried by Dariday sa Marogong.

Gomalaw Besaegan from Bogabongan a Ragat suggested that he has heard about the tale of pair beautiful princesses in a place called Bembaran in Dalinding a Sebangan. He further exclaimed how difficult it is to sail to that kingdom being always curtained by fog, well-guarded, and never been invaded.

Dariday sa Marogong has sworn "I shall no longer wait for another day to let the sun rise without my departure for I shall find out whether there is some truth to the dream that I had experienced. One more thing, I will never agree with what will prevent me from going to a foreign place across the sea. I ordered you to stay and wait for my come back for if I cannot return in a year then choose a new king for our kingdom."

Along his journey, a rich and well-developed kingdom like Taratakan a Oray has caught his attention. He began a fresh move by transforming or disguising himself as a Samar sa Odayawan to hide himself from the Datu he had just seen. Bantogen for his part, upon seeing him, also disguised himself as Madem or Manobo sa Layonan.

Samar: where was the place you came from? May I know why were you here?

Manobo: I am sorry to tell you that I have no place for I am like a bird wandering around. I am actually stationed here to watch anyone who comes by for I shall not allow him to pass here. I ask you, O Samar, go back to your place where you came from for I won't allow you to get in!

Samar: O Manobo sa layonan, when I came here after leaving the kingdom where I came from, my purpose was not to give trouble because I come looking for peace. However, if it happens that I cannot avoid trouble, that nothing I do can prevent it, then today, at this moment, it is my intention to create some disturbance on the waters. Should you do as you have told me that you will block my way so that I cannot achieve my purpose, then I swear, may I die right now if I shall not cut you down with my kampilan ipagerag, yes you, yourself shall test its blade.

Manobo: I challenge you to a fight in a truly fierce battle wherein we agree that in a fair fight, if I lose, if you defeat me, then I promise that I myself will become your subject and will be ready to obey all that you will ask, command me to do but if it happens that you will not match me in this grand battle then you will be my follower and I will make of you as a slave, my manservant in otawan to serve all my needs and wishes.

Samar: Dear Manobo sa layonan, if your aim is to do battle with me in a truly grand fight then I accept all your terms, but I want to state that I desire peace but if I am obliged to fight, then it is to my liking because there is no trouble or any typhoon that I avoid for I am already used to crossing bridges to the next world passing over unknown waters.

The two fought furiously on the vast shore with their kampilan and kelong scattering the rocks around as they clashed down to the sea up to the clouds then to the land of palm trees as if its leaves were cut down then reached the area of the cogon grass as the area was scattered by a storm.

Magaraay Anonen, staying up above the clouds, saw the fair fight and had recognized the Samar as Dariday sa Marogong and the Manobo as Bantogen and soon sent a thick cloud in between them so as to blind them from each other: bring Bantogen back to Bembaran and place Dariday sa Marogong on top of the Lakongan Minombaw.

A strong wind began to sweep all the thick clouds that stood guard over the spacious lamin of Inambayanan a Oray. Dariday sa Marogong suddenly was fascinated at the time he saw the magnificent lamin beneath the clouds. He decided to go up there and ask the princess if she might know about the great place of Bembaran.

Dinagoyanan a Sirig, accompanied the princess, saw prince Dariday sa Marogong travelling fast on the pathway of the thick clouds. She presumed that this stranger man is from a foreign land as rich, famous, prestige and same rank as they. Inambayanan a Oray warned her, even if it will cause their death, never to tell the prince her name and their own place for they are not so sure if he be an enemy of Bembaran who might take them by force and become their slaves.

The young prince followed an etiquette upon entering the Lamin. There they welcome him, offered a seat and a food, betel nut squid, to eat. The princess assumed that the prince was exhausted and tired from his journey so she offered a well-prepared bed for him to recline or sleep.

The prince once asked out of curiosity about her name and how come they are living in a lamin found there in the airy heights. The princess responded politely and rationally that if they had such place, they would not be there in the sky. As for her name, she exclaimed that she never heard herself being called.

The young prince took five full days for the length of his stay in the high spacious lamin. He had realized that he could never win any discussions with the wise princess with keen intellect. Now the prince was looking very sick and restless. Upon knowing this, the princess ordered Sirigen to give him the special life-giving water to cure his fever and prepare him a refreshing shew of betel quid which will make him better.

Dariday sa Marogong filled with a strange longing of his native land and truly missed his parents. The princess asked him his name, place, and the name of his great king. The young prince introduced himself in detail but later on, the princess was left in doubt and made a thought that the real cause of his grief was a loved one left at home for a king before being crowned is accompanied with a wife.

The young prince exclaimed "Do you think this friendship of ours which we have is something I hold seriously, not a joke? Our friendship is something precious for I swear, may I die right now, my name be forever lost if I am married, have a wife who I have left behind at home. Now the young prince would depart for a short while, he made a promise that he shall return to this high and wide luxurious lamin.

Bantogen who came together with his son Lumna had reached the tree Bangkonaw Madanding, the big palace of Magaraay Anonen above heavens. He made a request to fetch her own dearest sister whom they long so much. Magaraay Anonen has agreed upon his request.

Suddenly, the beautiful world had changed, the depths of the sea got darkened and it rained while the sun shone, the weather, as there appeared the rainbow, the pathway of the evil spirits. Every now and then, it rained the raindrops red as ripe betelnuts then a thick fog covered the earth as a powerful wind blew, the Sageseng Magondog which can destroy houses completely. Now the lamin rose and spiraled up, floating in the airy heights back to the kingdom of Iliyan a Bembaran.

Celebrating the return of their very princess, now was heard cannons firing followed by the music played from the kolintang, bright flags flying high and the variety of games now began. The sound of festive music was heard in the kingdoms around the place. Each family who had a young man of royal ancestry and gifted with handsome features began to prepare their ships to go to Bembaran to propose marriage ties with royal house.

Dariday sa Marogong suddenly remembered his dearest sweetheart whom he had left in her floating lamin. He made a request Diwata sa Magaw, the Tominoray ko langit, to send over a sweet breeze laden with fragrant odors so as to induce sleep on all who smell, the people of this resplendent torogan.

After five days of travelling, he decided to take a huge leap up into the airy heights but the lamin was nowhere to be found. Walking on the vast shore of the tranquil sea, he saw a species of palm trees with yellow leaves and began to cut the plants. A short while, a complaining voice was heard from the plants. The young prince apologized and accepted a punishment. When the tonong Magaraay Anonen asked him, the young prince took the chance of asking in what place now lives the very beautiful princess whose lamin was built in the clouds?

The tonong answered that the princess named Inambayanan a Oray has gone down in Magalinday Bembaran. The young prince was advised to transform himself into a Samar for in less than two days, a beautiful sailing vessel would arrive going to the kingdom of Bembaran.

After seven days of sailing both night and day without stopping finally sighted the magic sea of Bembaran. Baratamay Lumna who was walking gracefully making his way on the vast expanse of the seashore, saw the very handsome datu invited him to join the sipa game for those who can succeed in kicking the ball to reach and enter through the spacious lamin will win the princess, his aunt.

To begin, he played with the ball when it was first thrown to him, the gaudily shining rattan ball and he went around the place four times, the ball not once touching the ground, but just as high as his head and on the fifth time, he kicked with such force that away it flew to the lamin of Borantakan and as if calculated, it landed directly right in front of the very lovely princess, the Inambayanan Oray.

The young prince was given a chance to introduce himself in front of the crowd and will accept all what is asked as a dowry in Iliyan a Bembaran. One of Datus named Daranda challenged the young prince requesting to fill up the whole space lama of the torogan with all the man-eating crocodile with their gold necklaces!

The young prince responded "if that is your demand then I accept it. In a very short while, you will see here in front of you what you exactly demanded. At once, a sharp thunderbolt struck the shore, a strong wind suddenly blew over the sea as waves dashed against the lama as there now crawling all the man-eating crocodiles with their gold necklaces.

Bantogen and Madali were then informed that this was the demand of Daromimbang Daranda. Bantogen got very angry but soon welcome the prince with the blessings of peace for he is the grandson of Ayoong Pakapenag.

Finally, a big ship has come looking for their young prince, Dariday sa Marogong. The young prince, accompanied by Lumna, was very happy seeing his family once more. He was now at the stage of formal discussion on dowry requirements when suddenly out of the blue, the nori Sampiri sa Darimbang, had been flying over Kadaan informing them that the people there in big numbers are ready, after a few days, to launch big invasion on Taratakan a Oray.

Dariday sa Marogong told his people to stay here in Bembaran to discuss all what is required formally so that the royal marriage plans can then succeed. He must leave them for he has to defend his country, the dear Taratakan a Oray.

The big army of Kadaan fell like nuts cut off neatly by the sharp swords of of Ayonan sa Darimbang as well as that of Lumna. There soon arrived, landed quickly in Taratakan a Oray to reinforce the defense made by Ayonan sa Darimbang, Bantogen, and Madali.

How can you find fault with great Paramata bantogen as well as the brave Madali both famous names in the field of battle, recognized by warriors throughout the whole world being known for having no equal in their expertise in wielding the sword for one swing to the right cut in half, ten men, and a hard swing to the left brought down another ten warriors.

Nothing could be heard but groans from all the people who were wounded. Some of the enemy ran to the far mountain to hide there while others ran quickly back to their big boats. Others had to surrender and thus all of them were considered as captives of war of all the great people of Darimbang and Bembaran. At this point it was clear, to all that the war was really over in Taratakan a Oray and peace had come back and with it, the kingdom settled to normal.

In their resplendent torogan, saw clearly by himself that there was nothing left undone and it was time to discuss arrangements regarding the wedding itself of his future in-law, the young king, Ayonan sa Darimbangin Iliyan a Bembaran. Now he sent orders to call for the Batara miya alim to preside over the marriage of Ayonan sa Darimbang with the very lovely princess the Inambayanan a Oray. After the nuptials had all been celebrated, as agreed upon, it came to pass that that the newlyweds sailed on a big boat on the serene sea as they made their way directly to Taratakan a Oray.

